

A Wavelength-Scaled Ultra-Wide Bandwidth Array

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Introduction

An ultra-wideband antenna array design concept is presented that achieves the same functionality of traditional single-element-based ultra-wideband arrays using multiple elements that are scaled in size from the base high-frequency element, resulting in significantly fewer elements overall. For an array with 8:1 bandwidth, a fully functional design can be achieved with fewer than 16% of the original element count – i.e. 6.4x fewer elements, and the need for only 11% of the original electronics – a reduction factor of 9.2x, while maintaining the same array footprint. This novel array design leads to a significant reduction in weight and most importantly – a significant reduction in the cost to construct hardware and electronics; all while maintaining the same performance capacity of a traditional wideband antenna array.

Design Details

In previous work, the Naval Research Laboratory explored a design concept for ultra-wideband antenna arrays that featured a high-frequency core comprised of the usual wideband flared-notch elements surrounded by concentric rings of increasingly larger elements, the idea being that a fixed-size beam could be achieved at different frequency breakpoints by exciting a portion of the array for a given frequency of operation [1]. At the time, the concept was difficult to verify numerically due to the multitude of element types, and in practice, would have been too complex to implement. Recently, more powerful analysis tools have made it possible to test a more practical implementation of what we call the wavelength-scaled array concept [2]. This new approach to ultra-wide bandwidth array design, depicted in Figure 1, has core regions of different-sized elements that function for overlapping frequency bands, yet preserves critical mutual coupling paths. Note that there are *not* three separate/interleaved arrays – it is one continuous array in which different elements work collectively for a given frequency. As explained in the intro, this makes it possible to realize the full potential of an ultra-wideband array using far fewer elements than the traditional approach. These initial numerical studies gave us confidence the concept would work reasonably well compared to traditional ultra-wideband arrays, and considering the potential for cost savings, a practical design study was initiated.

In this paper, we present a functional wavelength-scaled array prototype design. It is based on a all-metal high-frequency flared notch design presented in a separate

paper [3]. The base high-frequency element is designed to function over roughly 1-8GHz, the mid-frequency element operates from 1-4GHz, and the low-frequency element works from 1-2GHz. Two test configurations were designed – a linear array configuration (see Figure 2) and a dual-polarized planar array configuration (see Figure 3). Each configuration is assembled from modular sub-arrays that are of the same size. For example, an 8-element sub-array of high-frequency elements has the same dimensions as a 4-element sub-array of mid-frequency elements and also the same dimensions as a 2-element sub-array of low-frequency antennas. The same holds true for the dual-polarized cores – 8x8 cores of high-frequency elements, 4x4 cores of mid-frequency elements, and 2x2 cores of low-frequency elements all have the same footprint. Test fixtures are designed in such a way that the modular cores can be arranged in many different configurations to meet custom specifications, etc. The cores are cut via wire-EDM technology and feature a simple proprietary SMA feed design that requires no soldering. In fact, the entire configuration can be assembled with a handful of bolts and re-configures just as easily. Based on the overall footprint, the prototype array achieves a 12 degree fixed beamwidth at the frequency break points of 2GHz, 4GHz, and 8GHz.

Results

For the linear array, construction is complete and the S-Parameter matrix has been fully characterized. Figure 4 shows the comparison between the measured VSWR of selected elements of the linear array (several of each type). For reference, the elements are numbered 1-16 starting from the high-frequency edge of the array in Figure 2. Measured comparisons are with the infinite (ideal) simulation for the given element type. From the plots, it is evident that the elements perform similar in the wavelength-scaled environment to the infinite environment. Note that the elements require a two-dimensional array lattice to function at the low end of the band. At the conference, more meaningful comparisons with simulations of the entire finite array will be presented, including scan performance characterization. Further, pattern measurements across the active bandwidth of the array will be taken with passive beam formers over several fixed scan angles to evaluate the effects of the wavelength-scaled environment on the shape of the beam.

To date, for the dual-polarized array only the 8x8 core of high-frequency elements has been completed and partially validated with measurements. When fully completed, similar measurements will be performed on the dual-polarized configuration including characterization of cross-polarization and related benchmarks.

Discussion

A functional wavelength-scaled prototype array has been presented. The array is based on a solid-metal design that is modular and easily reconfigurable. If successful, this design study may lead to more affordable ultra-wide bandwidth

arrays. In a related study, the University of Massachusetts, Amherst has been applying the concepts of wavelength-scaled array design to balanced-antipodal Vivaldi antennas [4]. This work is sponsored by the Office of Naval Research.

References

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Figure 1. Depiction of the Wavelength-Scaled Array Concept

Figure 2. Prototype linear wavelength-scaled array

Figure 3. Dual-polarized prototype array (construction partially completed)

Figure 4. Comparing measured VSWR to infinite (ideal) case